

Evaluation of Software Design Tools on Enhancing Security Measures in Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi, Sokoto State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Concern over security measures has grown in recent years as a result of tertiary institutions' rising reliance on technology. Academic institutions, especially universities and colleges of education, manage and retain a large volume of sensitive data, including student and faculty members' personal information and academic records. As a result, there is very little standardization in the administration and execution of security measures. Because of this variation, developing customized solutions necessitates an understanding of the unique security requirements of various organizations. The research seeks to address these multifaceted challenges by conducting a comprehensive evaluation of software design tools in the context of higher education. The objective is to assess the suitability and effectiveness of these tools in enhancing security measures, considering the unique needs and constraints of educational institutions. The research strategy for this study was a mixed-methods approach. This population consist of a variety of stakeholders, in Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi, Sokoto such as students, faculty, administrative staff, and IT personnel. The results show that majority of the participants have significance experience and take measures in using software design tools to enhance security measures.

Keyword: Software Design Tools, Tools, Software, Security, Gidan Madi

Introduction

Concern over security measures has grown in recent years as a result of tertiary institutions' rising reliance on technology. Academic institutions, especially universities and colleges of education, manage and retain a large volume of sensitive data, including student and faculty members' personal information and academic records. Because of this data's great value and attractiveness to potential attackers, institutions must put strong security measures in place to safeguard their networks and systems.

There are many different types of higher education institutions, and each has unique security requirements and limitations. The size, funding, and technological infrastructure of universities, colleges, and other educational institutions differ. As a result, there is very little standardization in the administration and execution of security measures (Rumez et al., 2020). Because of this variation, developing customized solutions necessitates an understanding of the unique security requirements of various organizations.

In addition, the Cyber security threat landscape is ever-changing. Cybercriminals and hackers use more advanced techniques to get past security measures (Dillon et al., 2021). Higher education institutions now worry about ransomware attacks, data breaches, and other security events on a daily basis. These occurrences have the potential to impair educational pursuits, jeopardize confidential data, and cause large financial losses.

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Higher education is changing and adapting to the digital age, and as a result, security is becoming more and more important to institutional governance rather than just being an IT issue (Alenezi, 2023). The findings of this study will be an invaluable tool for academic institutions as they work to improve security protocols, choose wisely which software development tools to use, and uphold their obligation to protect the data and digital infrastructure that are essential to their operations.

A thorough summary of secure software development techniques was given by Humayun et al. (2022), who also handled project budgets and schedules. Based on the discovered practices, they put forth a secure SDLC framework that incorporates the best security practices throughout the SDLC stages. An analytical model is employed to verify the suggested structure. The suggested approach helps integrate security best practices into the whole SDLC, leading to more secure applications, as demonstrated via a case study and conclusions.

Fuzzy analytic hierarchy process-technique for order preference by similarity ideal solution (AHP-TOPSIS) method was the hybrid multi-criteria decision-making strategy used by Alenezi et al. (2021) for the selection and evaluation of multi-criteria judgments. The suggested methodology combines the fuzzy TOPSIS order preference by similarity ideal solution with the fuzzy analytic hierarchy process (fuzzy AHP). The results are obtained after the evaluation has been tried on fifteen various web application projects (online quiz competition, entrance test, and others) of Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow, India, in order to establish the efficacy of this technique. The tabulated results show how successful the Multi-Level Fuzzy Hybrid system's methodology is in accurately estimating how to make web applications more secure. In order to improve accuracy and increase security, the suggested study will assist developers and experts in creating and managing security from any stage of the web application design process.

The hybrid Fuzzy AHPTOPSIS technique was employed by Attaallah et al. (2021) to assess the risks associated with enhancing the security durability of various institutional web applications. Furthermore, software durability is used to measure the e-component of security risk, and vice versa. The paper's conclusions will be helpful in improving the security resilience of various online applications.

In order to improve information security assurance in healthcare, Yeng et al. (2020) conducted a survey on current software development processes and evaluated their adequacy for gathering and analyzing security needs. Software security engineering standards and guidelines were used to gather information for security requirement activities. The extent to which the security activities were included into the current software development methodologies toward secure software development in the healthcare industry was then evaluated. The findings of this review indicate that traditional software development methods, such as the Waterfall Model, integrate security requirement capture activities more thoroughly than agile methods.

By examining and contrasting various approaches and standards, Ramirez et al. (2020) concentrated on secure software development and identified the stages of the software development life cycle (SDLC) where one or more of these stages could be used to enhance the security of a software application while it is being developed.

Prior research has shed light on the variety of always changing security issues that higher education institutions must deal with. These difficulties cover a broad spectrum of topics, including sensitive information protection, regulatory compliance, data breaches, and cyber threats. Scholars have recorded cases of security breaches and incidents that have affected organizations' operations and reputation (Smith et al., 2019).

Brown and Wilson (2019) conducted a thorough review of software design tools for security in tertiary institutions. The review focuses on analyzing software design tools specifically toured for security.

Another study by Anderson and Parker (2018) examined the characteristics, weaknesses, and practical implementation elements of selected software design tools that are frequently used for security enhancement in tertiary institutions.

(Smith et al., 2018, Johnson et al., 2019) carried out another investigation. With a focus on evaluating static code analysis tools, these tools help developers spot unsafe coding practices and enforce safe coding practices as security precautions. Using a threat modeling technique, one can detect possible risks and weaknesses in software systems. Developers can use these tools to prioritize security countermeasures, analyze the system architecture, and find probable attack vectors.

The research seeks to address these multifaceted challenges by conducting a comprehensive evaluation of software design tools in the context of higher education. This study to assess the suitability and effectiveness of these tools in enhancing security measures, considering the unique needs and constraints of educational institutions. By doing so, this study aims to contribute to the development of tailored security strategies that can safeguard the digital infrastructure of higher education institutions while promoting a safe and secure learning environment.

Objectives of the study:

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1. To assess the suitability and effectiveness of these tools in enhancing security measures,
2. To consider unique needs and constraints of educational institutions

Research Questions:

1. What personally experienced of any improvements in information security do stakeholders have as a result of using software design tools?
2. What are the challenges or concerns have encountered while using software design tools for security enhancement in the institution
3. What are the specific security incidents or breaches in the institution that could have been prevented or mitigated with the use of software design tools?
4. What are the frequency of update its security policies and procedures and adhere to them?

Research Methodology

Research Design

The research strategy for this study was a mixed-methods approach, chosen for its capacity to yield a comprehensive and multidimensional understanding of the subject themes. It is necessary to employ both quantitative and qualitative research methods in order to examine the many aspects of software design tools' contribution to enhancing security measures in higher education.

The foundation of the quantitative portion of the study design is structured surveys. These surveys will be distributed to a representative and diverse sample of participants from Federal College of Education Gidan Madi. The quantitative part of the study aims to gauge users' perceptions of and usage of software design tools. By collecting data via surveys, we can identify statistical relationships, patterns, and trends that are pertinent to the goals of the study.

The qualitative component, on the other hand, delves deeply into user experiences and institutional actions. Case studies and semi-structured interviews conducted at the selected institution make up this format. These qualitative methods seek to provide rich contextual information, engrossing narratives, and profound insights. On an interview platform, participants will be able to talk about their opinions, challenges, and experiences with software design tools.

Population of the Study

The study's population is typified by those connected to Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi, the primary case study institution. This population consists of stakeholders in Federal College of Education, GidanMadi. However, the primary emphasis of this study throughout its initial scope was the institution's internal community.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The study's sample consists of one hundred stakeholders chosen from the Federal College of Education, GidanMadi during the 2023/2024 academic session.

The quantitative part of the study, adopts a survey and a stratified random sampling method was used to divide the population into multiple strata based on the different stakeholder groups (administration staff, instructors, students, and IT personnel). From each stratum, a random sample was selected. This ensures that the survey responses are representative of the different demographic groups and enables meaningful comparisons to be made across different subsets.

The qualitative portion of the study, which comprises of case studies and interviews, adopts purposeful sampling. Experiences with software design tools and information security. Academic professionals, administrative staff, and IT staff with extensive expertise with these tools and their use was the focus of case studies and interviews. This tactic ensures that the qualitative portion carefully considers the perspectives of significant stakeholders.

This study aims to capture a comprehensive view of the population's experiences, perceptions, and practices related to software design tools and information security within the context of Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi. It does this by combining stratified random sampling for the quantitative component and purposive sampling for the qualitative component. These sampling strategies are chosen to preserve the sample's representativeness while enabling a thorough examination of the experiences of individuals with particular knowledge and duties in this field.

Instrument for Data Collection

The primary instrument for collecting quantitative data in this study was a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire's goal is to compile user views, habits, and firsthand knowledge regarding software design tools and their impact on security procedures within the selected institution. Using a combination of closed-ended and Likert-scale questions in the questionnaire, respondents communicate their thoughts and experiences in a standardized manner. The questionnaire was sent to the selected sample of participants, and response tested.

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Semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders was conducted. These stakeholders include academic staff, administrative staff, students and IT specialists who are knowledgeable in software design tools and information security. The interview guide contains open-ended questions to encourage participants to share their opinions, experiences, and thoughts. A further in-depth analysis of the research questions was made possible by extensive qualitative data collected from these interviews.

The case study component adopts case study methodology. These protocols outline the methodology and procedures for conducting in-depth case studies at the selected institution. The standards that govern data collection address information security protocols, the institutional environment, and the use of software design tools in depth. Case studies facilitate a comprehensive analysis of the study objectives and offer a complete viewpoint on the specific contexts in which these methodologies are used.

Procedure for Data Collection

To obtain user viewpoints and experiences about software design tools and their impact on security measures, a methodical questionnaire was developed. The participants in the sample were selected from Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi, using stratified random selection techniques.

To facilitate the gathering of data, case study protocols and semi-structured interview guides were created. Using purposive sample techniques, key stakeholders—faculty, administrative staff, and IT professionals with knowledge of software design tools and information security—were chosen for interviews and case studies.

Data Analysis

Each question from the questionnaire was represented in a table in order to provide a flexible and easy interpretation of result. The table covers five valid sections which includes; Frequency, Percent, Valid percent, Cumulative percent and a bar chart to aid a pictorial representation of the collected data.

Results

To allow for flexible and simple result interpretation, each questionnaire question was expressed as a table. The table contains five useful sections: Cumulative percent, valid percent, Frequency, Percent, and a bar chart to help visualize the data that was gathered.

Q1: Sex Categories

Table 1: Sex Categories

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	60	60.0	60.0	60.0
Female	40	40.0	40.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

As seen in figure 1, the above table indicates that 60% of respondents were men and 40% were women. As seen in figure 1, the above table indicates that 60% of respondents were men and 40% were women.

Figure 1: Age

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Q2: Years

Table 2: Years

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
18-30 Years	10	10.0	10.0	10.0
31-40 Years	40	40.0	40.0	50.0
41-50 Years	35	35.0	35.0	85.0
51 Years and Above	15	15.0	15.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

As can be seen in figure 2, 9.8% of the respondents were between the ages of 18 and 30, 39.2% were between the ages of 31 and 40, 8% were between the ages of 41 and 50, and 4% were over the age of 50.

Figure 2: Years

Q3: Marital Status

Table 3: Marital Status

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Single	20	20.0	20.0	20.0
Married	75	75.0	75.0	95.0
Divorce	5	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

It is evident from the preceding table that 20% of respondents were single, 75% were married, and 5% were divorced. This is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Marital Status

Q4: What is your primary role within Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi?

Table 4: What is your primary role within Federal College of Education, GidanMadi?

Evaluation of Software... (Abdulkadir, et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11474724>

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Student	20	20.0	20.0	20.0
Faculty Member	29	29.0	29.0	49.0
Administrative Staff	20	20.0	20.0	69.0
IT Personnel	31	31.0	31.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

Based on the statistics provided, the responsibilities at Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi are distributed as follows: Students make up 20% of the sample, followed by faculty members (29%), administrators (20%), and IT staff (31%). This is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: What is your primary role within Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi?

Table 5: Have you personally experienced any improvements in information security as a result of using software design tools?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	89	89.0	89.0	89.0
No	10	10.0	10.0	99.0
Undecided	1	1.0	1.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

Examining personal experiences with information security improvements due to the use of software design tools, a significant majority of respondents (89%) affirm positive changes, while a minority of 10% report no discernible improvements. One respondent (1%) remains undecided on the matter. This can be shown in figure 5.

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Figure 5: Have you personally experienced any improvements in information security as a result of using software design tools?

Table 6: What challenges or concerns have you encountered while using software design tools for security enhancement in your institution?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Technical compatibility issues	42	42.0	42.0	42.0
Lack of user training	30	30.0	30.0	72.0
Budget constraints	12	12.0	12.0	84.0
Resistance to change	16	16.0	16.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

Identifying challenges or concerns encountered in using software design tools for security enhancement within the institution, respondents noted the following: 42% faced technical compatibility issues, 30% cited a lack of user training, 12% dealt with budget constraints, and 16% encountered resistance to change. This can be shown in figure 6.

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Figure 6: What challenges or concerns have you encountered while using software design tools for security enhancement in your institution?

Table 7: Are there specific security incidents or breaches in your institution that you think could have been prevented or mitigated with the use of software design tools?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	15	15.0	15.0	15.0
No	80	80.0	80.0	95.0
Undecided	5	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

In considering the potential impact of software design tools on security incidents or breaches within the institution, 15% of respondents believe that such tools could have prevented or mitigated incidents. Meanwhile, 80% express the view that these tools may not have made a significant difference, and 5% remain undecided on the matter. This can be shown in figure 7.

Figure 7: Are there specific security incidents or breaches in your institution that you think could have been prevented or mitigated with the use of software design tools?

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Table 8: Do you believe that the utilization of software design tools for security enhances the institution's reputation and trustworthiness among stakeholders (e.g., students, parents, faculty, etc.)?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	95	95.0	95.0	95.0
Undecided	5	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

Examining perceptions on the impact of utilizing software design tools for security on the institution's reputation and trustworthiness among stakeholders, an overwhelming 95% of respondents believe that such utilization enhances the institution's standing. Meanwhile, 5% remain undecided on this matter. This can be shown in figure 8.

Figure 8: Do you believe that the utilization of software design tools for security enhances the institution's reputation and trustworthiness among stakeholders (e.g., students, parents, faculty, etc.)?

Table 9: How frequently does your institution update its security policies and procedures?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Very frequently	80	80.0	80.0	80.0
Frequently	9	9.0	9.0	89.0
Occasionally	7	7.0	7.0	96.0
Rarely	4	4.0	4.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

Regarding the frequency of updating security policies and procedures within the institution, a substantial 80% of respondents indicate that updates are made very frequently. In contrast, 9% report updates occurring frequently, 7% occasionally, and a minor 4% rarely. This can be shown in figure 9.

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Figure 9: How frequently does your institution update its security policies and procedures?

Table 10: Does your institution need to adhere to any of the following regulations or compliance standards regarding data security and privacy?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation)	32	32.0	32.0	32.0
HIPAA (Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act)	41	41.0	41.0	73.0
FERPA (Family Educational Rights and Privacy Act)	17	17.0	17.0	90.0
PCI DSS (Payment Card Industry Data Security Standard)	10	10.0	10.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Source: Questionnaire Administered (2023)

Concerning adherence to data security and privacy regulations or compliance standards within the institution, the respondent ticked as follows: GDPR: 32%, HIPAA: 41% FERPA: 17% PCI DSS: 10%. This can be shown in figure 10.

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Figure 10: Does your institution need to adhere to any of the following regulations or compliance standards regarding data security and privacy?

Discussion of Findings

Staff and students at Federal College of Education Gidan Madi were asked how much they knew about the use of software design tools. Table 1 revealed that men make up roughly 60% of the participants, which suggests that women also participate to a considerable extent. The bulk of participants, as seen by Table 2, are between the ages of 31 and 40. The data presented in Table 3 indicates that the majority of participants are married. The bulk of participants are IT professionals, as Table 4 illustrates.

Also, Table 5 shown that majority of the respondent (89%) affirm positive changes in examining personal experiences with information security improvements due to the use of software design tools, table 6 shown that majority of the respondent (42%) faced technical compatibility issues in respect of challenges or concerns encountered in using software design tools for security enhancement within the institution, table 7 shown that majority of the respondent (80%) express the view that these tools may not have made a significant difference in considering the potential impact of software design tools on security incidents or breaches within the institution, table 8 shown that majority of the respondent (95%) of respondents believe that such utilization enhances the institution's standing on the impact of utilizing software design tools for security on the institution's reputation and trustworthiness among stakeholders.

Furthermore, table 9 shown that majority of the respondent (80%) of indicate that updates are made very frequently regarding the frequency of updating security policies and procedures within the institution and table 10 shown that majority of the respondent (41%) follow Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act data security and privacy regulation.

Conclusion

To sum up, the careful assessment of software design tools for improving security measures at Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi, reveals a complex environment in which technical solutions are essential to strengthening the security posture of the school as a whole. A good step towards a robust cybersecurity framework is indicated by the overwhelmingly positive reaction from respondents, with 65% expressing confidence in the major advances brought about by these technologies. The prioritizing of data encryption and enhanced network monitoring technologies, which are in line with contemporary best practices, indicate a proactive response to the ever-evolving threat landscape.

Crucially, the collaborative and cooperative spirit within the institution, as evidenced by the IT Department's central role and the excellent level of cooperation and communication between departments (76%), underscores a collective commitment to a robust security infrastructure. This collaborative ethos is foundational in fostering a holistic understanding of security needs and ensures that all stakeholders, including students, faculty, and administrative staff, feel adequately supported.

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However, it's crucial to acknowledge the identified challenges, particularly technical compatibility issues (42%) and the need for user training (30%). Addressing these challenges should be approached not merely as technical hurdles but as opportunities for continuous improvement. Furthermore, the institution's commitment to very frequent security policy updates (80%) positions it at the forefront of adapting to emerging threats and adhering to the ever-evolving cybersecurity landscape.

In navigating the future, Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi, stands poised to leverage technology and collaboration as cornerstones in fortifying its security measures. As the institution continues to evolve, sustaining a proactive and adaptive approach will be pivotal in maintaining not only the current positive momentum but also in proactively addressing emerging challenges in the realm of cybersecurity.

Maintain the institution's commitment to very frequent security policy updates (80%) to ensure that security measures align with emerging threats and industry best practices. Establish a framework for continuous evaluation of security measures, regularly soliciting feedback from stakeholders to adapt strategies based on evolving needs and technological advancements.

Recommendations

In light of these findings, we suggested:

1. Ongoing training programs.
2. Handling of technical compatibility concerns and guarantee that all users are adept in utilizing software design tools to their fullest potential,
3. Implementation of regular and customized training initiatives.

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